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PECULIARITIES OF SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF THE PERSONALITY ART TECHNIQUES

ОСОБЛИВОСТІ САМОРОЗВИТКУ ОСОБИСТОСТІ АРТ-ЗАСОБМИ

Охарактеризовано арт-засоби як один з чинників саморозвитку, а саме як ефективну психологічну практику, що сприяє глибинному самопізнанню, саморозумінню та розвитку особистості; інтенсифікує процеси навчання та оволодіння професійно важливими компетенціями у сфері практичної психології; сприяє розвиткові професійно значущих рис, коригує самооцінку, самосприйняття, мотивацію, уявлення про професійну діяльність.

Ключові слова: *арт-засоби, особистісний розвиток, саморозвиток, психокорекція.*

Art techniques are means of correction and development through artistic creativity. The system of applying art tools in psychocorrectional practice was formed in the 40s and 50s of the last century in the UK and the USA. Based on a humanistic approach, artistic means pursue a single goal – the harmonious development of the individual, the expansion of the possibilities of his or her social adaptation through art. The uniqueness of the use of art tools lies in the fact that they make it possible to increase self-control, self-disclosure and self-development (Інжієвська, 2017).

The use of Art techniques is based on the mobilization of human creativity, internal mechanisms of self-regulation and meets the fundamental need for self-actualization: the disclosure of a wide range of human capabilities, the assertion of their individual and unique way of being in the world (Інжієвська, 2017).

Psycho-correctional work with the use of art helps people to form a more active life position. Regarding the issues of our dissertation, the idea of using the potential of art tools to develop the personal potential of future professionals is potentially fruitful. The advantages of Art techniques are the possibility of using them not only with those students who need psychological assistance in a difficult life situation, but also to promote their personal growth. The humanistic orientation of art tools allows creating conditions for self-actualization through creative expression and the search for transcendent life goals (Інжієвська, 2017).

Art techniques make it possible to realize one of the main principles of modern education – the possibility of organizing education as an active process that involves interaction. This allows future professionals to become more active and responsible for their work, to see new opportunities for expressing their own individuality. The skills that can be gained from this experience will allow

students to feel more comfortable, confident, and use this experience in their professional life (Інжієвська, 2017).

This idea is in line with the central idea of twenty-first century education discussed in the book by R. Acuff and D. Greenberg, who argue that education should help and support the development of personal potential of the individual. The authors believe that the main goal of education is to give learners the opportunity for their own development and the ability to participate in the development of the society to which they belong (Пурнис, 2008).

Art techniques have significant advantages over other psychological means. Let us note some of them: they are a means of free self-expression and self-knowledge; they are largely «insight-oriented»; they create an atmosphere of trust and understanding of the inner world of a person; they have no limits and restrictions on their use; in most cases, they evoke positive emotions in people, help to overcome apathy, lack of initiative, form an active life position and a positive worldview; are based on mobilization of the individual's creative potential, internal mechanisms of self-regulation and self-mobilization; are characterized by special «softness» of techniques and influences; are mainly a means of non-verbal communication (Інжієвська, 2017).

Art techniques, including individual drawing, group drawing, sculpture, and collage, help to realize the idea of a new education. Among them are:

- relieving stress and tension that students may experience;
- Assistance in exploring individual resources and desires;
- increasing the level of reflection by analyzing the results obtained in the process of work;
- facilitating experimentation in a safe environment;
- learning to think outside the box;
- considering creativity as a value of personal development (Інжієвська, 2017).

These advantages are valuable for supporting people and developing their personal potential. Art techniques help to overcome obstacles that prevent future professionals from developing creativity, such obstacles can be: a negative attitude towards personal potential, which may be socially conditioned, high anxiety, tension, and a reduced level of control (Інжієвська, 2017).

L. Podkorytova believes that the use of Art techniques combines some opposite dimensions, such as «emotions – thinking», «analysis – synthesis», «activity – passivity», etc. Thanks to this, artistic means teach a person to feel and think, to balance emotions and thinking, to combine rational and irrational in oneself, accepting them not as opposites, but as complementary parts of one's personality in its integrity. By integrating analysis and synthesis, Art techniques encourage a person to deep self-knowledge and create conditions for the synthesis of new things in oneself. Combining the active and the passive, creation and contemplation, Art techniques include powerful therapeutic mechanisms and direct their corrective influence on all structures and dimensions of the human

personality – from the physical through the mental to the spiritual (Подкоритова, 2011).

To summarize, let us define the peculiarities of using art tools for the personal development:

- interdisciplinarity, integrative use of art means promotes intra-psyche integration processes in both professional and personal spheres;

- proximity to direct psychological practice as a future professional activity contributes to the growth of one's readiness for it;

- the combination of educational and therapeutic processes in the classroom with the use of Art techniques contributes to a more effective assimilation of both purely professional knowledge, skills and abilities, as well as a deeper knowledge of one's own inner world, understanding of others;

- the combination of individual and group work contributes, on the one hand, to the manifestation of individuality, and on the other hand, to the socialization and adaptation of the individual;

- reflexivity of classes helps personal and professional self-awareness: «passing through» a particular methodology, the student learns more deeply and better understands the effect of the tools used in the classroom, which contributes to a more effective assimilation of professional knowledge;

- the creative atmosphere of the classroom provides an open, spontaneous, natural expression of the individuality of each student, reveals the creative potential;

- the creative process heals and transforms, helps to correct the personality;

- focusing on the inner world of the individual to some extent solves the problem of undergoing personal psychotherapy as a prerequisite for further successful professional activity;

- the combination of immersion in one's own emotions and analysis of the expressive product leads to insight and catharsis, and, therefore, ensures the spiritual growth of the individual;

- the positive experience gained as a result of the use of art tools becomes a source for the personal and professional growth of a person, a model for building humane relationships with people (Зинкевич-Евстигнеева, 2005).